

Research programme to share knowledge and improve uptake of new digital technologies in sheep and goat

farming

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101000471.

TRAINING AND PEER TO PEER DEMONSTRATION

Sm@RT POLICY BRIEFS

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Introduction

General introduction about the project

Sm@RT (Small Ruminant technologies –Precision Livestock Farming & Digital technologies for small ruminants) is a European network to share experience of new technologies for sheep and goats. It brings together a network of researchers, farmers and advisors to improve awareness of innovative tools, demonstrating their potential and possible return on investment.

Sm@RT involved 11 partners in 8 countries, and focus on dairy goats, dairy sheep and meat sheep farmers.

Sm@RT fostered exchanges of the experience on the use of technologies between farmers during demonstration days in innovative farms and digifarms.

Sm@RT enabled farmers to learn more about the available technologies to progress in their digitization process to meet their needs and objectives. Guidelines, cost-benefit analysis, farmers' testimonies and videos have been created to encourage uptake of solutions to needs.

Findings

In general, the findings of this project confirm that:

- Although only 15 % of farmers have technologies on their farms, 79% of them would like to use it to help with feeding/grazing, health and welfare, reproduction, flock/herd management, fattening and/or milking
- A total of 166 ranked needs were identified and 60 innovative technology solutions were proposed to the farmers.
- Training sessions on Digifarms and Farm Demonstrations on Innovative farms proved an ideal medium for peer-to-peer knowledge transfer regarding the use of technologies.
- The main barriers to uptake are linked to the cost of technologies, but also to the lack of training options, after-sales advice, confidence in one's skills and compatibility between the devices.
- Sharing of knowledge and experiences between farmers, researchers and other stakeholders in different countries proved invaluable.
- There is a lot of information regarding cost of technologies, but the information is often dispersed and not always in a format (or language) easy to understand or to adapt to one's farming situation. Cost-benefit analyses are necessary for farmers to fully decide on investing in technologies or not.
- It can be difficult for farmers to compare available technologies and know what will work for their system before purchasing. Training sessions and farmer testimonials helped with this.

The project identified 4 key messages, that are developed in policy briefs:

1. Focus on research needs
2. Peer-to-peer demonstration & training needs for farmers
3. Innovations on small ruminant farms
4. Adoption & uptake of innovative technologies

This policy brief focus on key message #2 - Peer-to-peer demonstration & training needs for farmers

*The recommendations identified in the four policy briefs have been developed during the life of the project by the partners and in collaboration with **over 1350** stakeholders during the project's participatory workshops.*

*The project carried out an initial online survey to capture farmers' opinions, which gathered **over 660** answers. A total of **52** national workshops have been conducted, together with **five** transnational workshops, **one** final seminar and **one** international visit. **Over 635** individual farmers' evaluations have been collected during **30** training sessions and farm demonstrations days on Digifarms and Innovative Farms.*

Recommendation at a glance

- **The evaluation of technologies is useful to assess stakeholder acceptance.**
- **Training sessions for farmers may be the key for improving knowledge exchange.**
- **Farmer's opinions are important to understand the potential uptake of technologies.**
- **Experimental Digifarms play an important role as reference centre for technologies.**
- **Private Innovative farms are useful for peer to peer information exchange.**

What is the challenge?

- There is a lack of uptake of innovative technologies by sheep and goat farmers in Europe and beyond.
- Although innovative technologies and digital solutions are widely accepted in other livestock industries (e.g. dairy cattle), the sheep and goat sectors are less inclined to invest and use technologies on their farms.
- This is despite the many potential benefits that could be had from using these innovative solutions, as seen in Sm@RT policy brief no. 3.
- It is not always easy to understand where the barriers to uptake lie, as there might be multiple and they depend on the innovative technology and farming system considered.

What did we learn from Sm@RT?

- Sm@RT conducted a series of training and demonstration sessions to evaluate technologies proposed by the countries and that answer the farmers' needs.
- In each country, in combination with the cost-benefit analysis, farmers and practitioners were invited to evaluate the technologies through 2 mechanisms: training days on the **Digifarms** and Demo days on **Innovative Farms**.
- Around the countries, a total of **380** opinions were collected during Digifarm sessions and **860** during Innovative farms.
- Training sessions on Digifarms and demonstration days on innovative farms have proved to be good instruments to foster practical knowledge among stakeholders. It has been a valuable transfer of information and skills between both the researchers, who had the opportunity to get farmers opinions, and farmers, who had a hands-on opportunity to try out various technologies and discuss with their peers the pros and cons without barriers due to educational level. The project has improved the **potential uptake of technologies** by the sector across Europe.
- This further reinforces the value of these events to help farmers make more informed decisions when considering which tools and technologies could be most beneficial to their farming system.

What do we recommend?

- ✓ **Provide detailed cost-benefit analysis of the innovative technologies, including scale of the business.**
- ✓ **Provide trainings for farmers interested in improving their knowledge on specific technologies.**
- ✓ **Provide a trial period, at least in experimental Digifarms, to test the technology before buying.**
- ✓ **Promote peer to peer knowledge exchange between stakeholders.**

